

MODEL FOR ADDRESSING NARCOTICS OFFENSES USING A RESTORATIVE JUSTICE APPROACH THROUGH REHABILITATION

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Abstract

Law No. 35 of 2009 on Narcotics incorporates a dual approach, combining a repressive strategy with severe sanctions, including the death penalty, and a rehabilitative approach for addicts. In practice, however, this has led to overcapacity in correctional facilities, a burdened judicial system, and weak offender rehabilitation. Recently, the discourse on restorative justice has emerged, although it has the potential to conflict with existing legal norms and societal moral values. This paper examines a model for addressing narcotics offenses through a restorative justice approach. This research is normative legal research. The approaches used include the statutory approach, conceptual approach, case approach, and sociological approach. The theoretical framework employed as an analytical tool encompasses sentencing theory, legislative theory, and development law theory. The findings indicate that a model for resolving narcotics offenses using a restorative justice approach through rehabilitation positions the drug user as a victim in need of recovery, rather than merely a criminal. The Attorney General's Guidelines No. 18 of 2021 have opened a space for rehabilitation; however, its authority remains weak as it is only internal. Therefore, the substance of these guidelines should be elevated into a Restorative Justice Law, thereby granting it national binding power, ensuring legal certainty, and promoting consistency in implementation.

Keywords: Narcotics, Rehabilitation, Restorative Justice.

INTRODUCTION

Globally, the number of narcotics abusers has reached 296 million people (5.8% of the population aged 15–64 years), an increase of 12 million compared to the previous year. In Indonesia (2023), the prevalence of narcotics abuse was recorded at 1.73%, or approximately 3.3 million people aged 15–64 years, with a significant increase observed among the 15–24 age group¹.

These data indicate that issues in law enforcement persist, despite the enactment of Law No. 35 of 2009 on Narcotics, which regulates prohibited acts, responsibilities, criminal sanctions, the establishment of the National Narcotics Agency (BNN), and the role of society. This regulation embodies a dual approach to eradication, namely a hard approach and a soft approach.

This is reflected in the imposition of specific minimum and maximum penalties, including life imprisonment and the death penalty, while at the same time providing space for rehabilitation of victims and addicts. Another equally important issue that warrants attention is the problem of overcapacity.

Inmates convicted of narcotics-related offenses are the largest contributors to overcrowding in correctional institutions (Lapas) and state detention centers (Rutan).

As of July 26, 2021, out of a total of 268,610 inmates, 139,088 individuals (51.8%) were incarcerated for narcotics cases. Over the past five years, the inmate population has increased by 130,000, and if this trend continues, it is projected to reach 400,000 within the next five years².

In its development, the resolution of narcotics-related criminal offenses has shifted towards approaches that emphasize restoration, involvement, facilitation, and a future-oriented focus aligned with the demands for a Restorative Justice approach. However, this approach may at times conflict with societal moral standards and other prevailing norms.

This approach is consistent with the evolving sense of justice within society, which favors more humane handling of relatively minor cases such as petty theft involving minimal losses so that they are no longer brought by prosecutors to trial.

Accordingly, prosecutors are now expected to pursue charges or take positions guided by the principles of restorative justice. This reflects one of the manifestations of prosecutorial discretion. Through such discretion, not all criminal cases must proceed to court and result in punishment³.

The response to resolutions based on the principles of restorative justice has given rise to various regulations, ranging from Law No. 11 of 2012 on the Juvenile Criminal Justice System to institutional regulations that provide the legal foundation for the application of restorative justice within the Indonesian National Police and the Attorney General's Office of the Republic of Indonesia. These regulations emphasize their role as *dominus litis*, focusing on the protection and recovery of addicts, users, and victims of narcotics.

Through a restorative justice approach that prioritizes rehabilitation, they are afforded the opportunity to recover from drug dependence. This is in line with the prosecutorial authority under the Indonesian Code of Criminal Procedure (KUHP), as well as Article 4(d) of Law No. 35 of 2009 on Narcotics, which guarantees medical and social rehabilitation for narcotics addicts and users.

The Attorney General's Office of the Republic of Indonesia, in cooperation with relevant ministries and agencies through a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU), has established the Adhyaksa Rehabilitation Center as a coordination hub for handling cases involving narcotics users, addicts, and victims.

This center differs from those operated by the National Narcotics Agency (BNN) or private institutions, as it functions to implement rehabilitation in accordance with the Attorney General's Guideline No. 18 of 2021 on the Implementation of Restorative Justice.

The guideline not only optimizes the resolution of narcotics cases through rehabilitation but also reduces state expenditure, since cases are concluded at the prosecution stage, while ensuring equal access to rehabilitation regardless of social status, in line with the mandate of Article 4(d) of Law No. 35 of 2009 on Narcotics.

METHODE

The type of research employed in this study is normative legal research, which views law as a system of norms. This type of research examines the principles, norms, and rules contained in legislation, court decisions, agreements, and doctrines. According to Peter Mahmud Marzuki, normative legal research aims to establish coherence, namely whether legal rules are consistent with legal norms, whether commands or prohibitions are in harmony with legal principles, and whether a person's actions conform to legal norms (not only legal rules) or legal principles⁴. As a form of legal research, and in line with the distinctive characteristics of legal scholarship, several approaches are applied in normative legal research, including:

- (a) The Statute Approach,
- (b) The Conceptual Approach,
- (c) The Sociological Approach, and
- (d) The Case Approach.

This study relies on literature or secondary data, which includes primary, secondary, and tertiary legal materials. The collection of legal materials was carried out through documentary study by recording information from relevant legal sources, whether normative in nature or conceptual. The recording process was conducted selectively to support and complement legal materials obtained from other sources.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Model for Resolving Narcotics Offenses Through Rehabilitation Using A Restorative Justice Approach

Efforts to address narcotics-related crimes in terms of substance must begin with policy formulation and criminal law reform. This step is crucial to realizing the nation's aspirations, namely to protect all the people of Indonesia and to achieve collective welfare. According to M. Solly Lubis, this means providing protection through the existing legal instruments and instruments of authority, so that in this country there exists an order or system of regulation that guarantees both moral and material, as well as physical and mental, well-being through the enforcement of law⁵.

Salah satu kegiatan dalam kebijakan penal adalah tahap formulasi, dalam hal ini adalah pembaharuan hukum pidana. Pembaharuan hukum pidana (*penal reform*) merupakan bagian dari kebijakan/ politik hukum pidana (*penal policy*). Politik kriminal, sebagai bagian dari politik hukum, terus mengalami perkembangan dari waktu ke waktu, sebagai usaha rasional dari masyarakat dalam menang-gulangi kejahatan. Menurut G. Peter Hoefnagels, politik kriminal adalah *'the rational organization of the social reaction to crime'*⁶.

One of the activities within penal policy is the formulation stage, namely criminal law reform. Criminal law reform (penal reform) constitutes a part of criminal law policy (penal policy). Criminal policy, as a component of legal policy, continues to evolve over time as a rational

effort by society to combat crime. According to G. Peter Hoefnagels, criminal policy is “*the rational organization of the social reaction to crime*”⁶. According to Sudarto, in relation to legal policy, it is the effort to realize sound regulations in accordance with the prevailing conditions and circumstances at a given time.

It represents the policy of the state, exercised through its competent authorities, to establish the desired regulations that are deemed capable of expressing the nation’s aspirations⁷. Based on the aforementioned considerations, Sudarto further states that criminal law policy (penal policy) is an effort to establish criminal legislation that is in accordance with the conditions and circumstances at a given time and for the future⁸.

Pursuant to Law Number 1 of 2023 concerning the Indonesian Criminal Code (New KUHP), the orientation of sentencing has significantly shifted compared to that under the previous Criminal Code. Article 51 stipulates the objectives of sentencing as follows: (a) to prevent the commission of criminal acts by upholding legal norms for the protection and safeguarding of society; (b) to rehabilitate offenders through guidance and supervision so that they may become good and useful members of society; (c) to resolve conflicts arising from criminal acts, restore balance, and bring a sense of security and peace within the community; and (d) to foster remorse and relieve offenders of their guilt. Furthermore, Article 52 states that sentencing is not intended to degrade human dignity.

From the provisions outlined above, it is evident that sentencing is no longer characterized by a retributive nuance, but rather aims to provide benefits, prevent future crimes, and, notably, introduces the concept of restoration. Furthermore, Article 70 paragraph (1) emphasizes that imprisonment should, as far as possible, not be imposed if certain circumstances are present, namely: (1) the defendant is a minor; (2) the defendant is over 75 (seventy-five) years of age; (3) the defendant has committed a criminal act for the first time; (4) the loss and suffering of the victim is not substantial; (5) the defendant has compensated the victim; (6) the defendant was unaware that the criminal act committed would cause significant harm; (7) the criminal act was committed due to strong incitement by another person; (8) the victim instigated or provoked the occurrence of the criminal act; (9) the criminal act resulted from circumstances unlikely to recur; (10) the defendant’s personality and behavior provide assurance that he or she will not commit another criminal act; (11) imprisonment would cause severe suffering for the defendant or his or her family; (12) non-custodial rehabilitation is expected to succeed for the defendant; (13) the imposition of a lighter sentence would not diminish the gravity of the offense; (14) the criminal act occurred within a family setting; and/or (15) the criminal act was the result of negligence. However, these provisions are limited by Article 70 paragraph (2), which stipulates that they do not apply to: (a) criminal acts punishable by imprisonment of five (5) years or more; (b) criminal acts subject to a mandatory minimum sentence; (c) certain criminal acts that pose serious danger or harm to society; or (d) criminal acts that cause losses to the state’s finances or economy.

Considering the various conceptions outlined above, the legal reforms required in the application of restorative justice values to narcotics abuse may be presented in the following table:

Table 1: Direction of Legal Reform

No.	Scope	Restorative Justice Value Content	Renewal / Improvement
1	Legal Products	RJ Substance	Strengthening the type through legislation
		Criteria and Limitations	Strengthening formulations in legislation
2	Material (Criminal Act Qualification)	Victim's Interest	Regulation of victim involvement, represented by community institutions concerned with criminal justice and narcotics issues
		Restoration of Condition	Regulation in the law emphasizing handling of narcotics abuse in terms of restoration
		Meetings of Parties	Regulating meetings/building agreements with other law enforcement agencies
		Case Termination	Regulation of case termination needs to be emphasized in the form of legislation, as it may conflict with the Criminal Procedure Code (KUHAP)
		Restorative Justice with Cases Proceeding	RJ does not only mean case termination; focus remains on restoration/reparation while still considering the benefits of sentencing
3	Formal (Institutional)	Institutions Focusing on Victim's Interests	Requires adjustments in the legislation of each law enforcement institution
		Integration between Law Enforcement and Non-Governmental Institutions	Emphasis in legislation and institutional regulations
		Inclusive Institutions	Emphasis in legislation and institutional regulations
		Authority to Terminate Cases	Emphasis in legislation and institutional regulations
4	Public Legal Awareness	Forgiveness from the Community	Emphasis in the law on the role of the community through social organizations (Ormas)
		Restoration / Eliminating the Retaliation Nuance	Emphasis that termination is for restoration, because Indonesian society still favors a retaliatory approach

Legal reform is necessary to ensure legal certainty that enhances order and ultimately leads to justice, as law functions as an instrument of social reform within the framework of development. Theo Huijbers asserts that the function of law is to safeguard the public interest within society, to protect human rights, and to realize justice in communal life. These three objectives are not mutually contradictory, but rather constitute the fulfillment of a single fundamental concept, namely that human beings must live within a society, and that such a society must be properly regulate⁹.

Considering the various conceptions above, the necessary legal reform in the application of restorative justice values strongly resonates with this policy direction, particularly with the Attorney General's Guideline Number 18 of 2021, specifically Chapter III on Pre-Prosecution. In this guideline, public prosecutors are required not only to examine the formal and material

completeness of a case, but also to take into account substantive aspects related to the status of the suspect, including the results of an integrated assessment. The guideline emphasizes that narcotics abusers should not automatically be sentenced to imprisonment, but may instead be placed in medical or social rehabilitation programs through a clear legal mechanism. Rehabilitation is positioned as a form of case resolution that is more beneficial than imprisonment, with the objective of restoring the offender so that they may once again function within society.

By adopting a rehabilitation-based approach through a Restorative Justice Act, the law can perform a dual function: maintaining order and legal certainty while simultaneously fulfilling the needs of human development, namely restoring drug abusers so that they may once again become productive members of society. This represents the manifestation of law as an instrument of development, structuring social processes to ensure that legal certainty and order are achieved. Based on the convergence of the two regulations mentioned above, the new Criminal Code (KUHP) provides the philosophical and normative foundation that punishment must be humanistic, educational, and restorative, while the Attorney General's Guideline offers the technical mechanism that enables the implementation of these principles, particularly in narcotics-related cases. Both are aligned in positioning law enforcement not merely as a repressive instrument, but also as a means to advance restorative justice, restore balance, and deliver tangible benefits for offenders, victims, and society at large.

Nevertheless, a fundamental weakness arises because the guideline does not fall within the hierarchy of Law No. 12 of 2011 on the Formation of Laws and Regulations. When analyzed through Hans Kelsen's *Stufenbau Theorie*, every legal norm is structured in a layered hierarchy, ranging from the basic norm (*grundnorm*) to lower-level regulations¹⁰.

At the apex lies the Constitution, followed by statutes, then government regulations, ministerial regulations, and finally internal institutional rules. The Attorney General's Guideline No. 18 of 2021 is positioned merely as an internal policy rule (*beleidsregel*) of an administrative nature. Consequently, within the normative hierarchy, this guideline does not possess binding authority over society at large, but applies solely within the Prosecutor's Office as an internal directive.

Therefore, the substance of the Attorney General's Guideline should ideally be elevated into a statute on Restorative Justice, particularly in resolving narcotics-related criminal offenses through rehabilitation. By being enacted at the statutory level, its status would be equivalent to other legislative instruments, thereby serving as the highest legal framework binding all law enforcement authorities (police, prosecutors, and judges), and ensuring legal certainty as well as consistency in its application. If realized, rehabilitation for narcotics abusers would no longer merely constitute an internal prosecutorial policy, but rather a legal right of the suspect/defendant guaranteed by law.

The incorporation of the substance of Attorney General's Guideline No. 18 of 2021 into a statute is also consistent with Mochtar Kusumaatmadja's theory of law as a means of social development, which asserts that "Law serves as an instrument of social reform." This principle underscores that law functions not only as a tool of social control but also as an instrument to

promote social transformation toward the better. In the context of narcotics policy, a legal framework that merely positions drug abusers as subjects of imprisonment fails to provide genuine reformatory value and, in fact, risks exacerbating social problems¹².

In view of the above concepts, the legal reforms required in institutional restructuring may be presented in the following table:

Table 2: The Direction of Institutional Legal Reform in the Resolution of Narcotics Crimes Through Restorative Justice

Aspect	Current Condition (Attorney General Guideline No. 18 of 2021)	Direction of Reform (Restorative Justice Law)	Practical Implications
Philosophical Foundation	The guideline is merely administrative and lacks strong legitimacy within the legal hierarchy.	The Restorative Justice Law positions rehabilitation as a legal right, aligned with the humanistic philosophy of punishment in the New Criminal Code.	Shifts the punishment paradigm from repressive to restorative; substance abusers are viewed as victims in need of rehabilitation.
Position in Legal Hierarchy	Only a <i>beleidsregel</i> (internal policy regulation), low in the Stufenbau Theorie hierarchy.	Equivalent to other laws, binding all law enforcement agencies and society.	Ensures uniform law enforcement at the national level; eliminates disparities in treatment across regions.
Purpose of Punishment	Emphasizes rehabilitation alternatives but is still limited to the technical scope of prosecution.	Establishes rehabilitation as the primary instrument for the recovery of substance abusers, not merely an alternative.	Substance abusers gain the right to rehabilitation as a form of legal protection, not just as a discretionary policy of authorities.
Binding Force	Applies internally within the prosecution institution; does not bind the police, courts, or the general public.	Binds all law enforcement agencies (police, prosecutors, judges) and provides legal guarantees for suspects/defendants.	Legal processes become more consistent; judges, prosecutors, and police share a unified reference for rehabilitation decisions.
Legal Certainty Guarantee	Weak, potentially conflicting with higher-level laws.	Provides consistent, uniform, and sustainable national legal certainty.	Reduces the risk of excessive criminalization of substance abusers; enhances public trust in the law.

CONCLUSION

Based on the above discussion, in the context of resolving narcotics offenses through rehabilitation using a restorative justice approach, this represents a legal reform that positions substance abusers not merely as offenders, but as individuals in need of recovery. This approach aligns with the punitive philosophy in the New Criminal Code, which emphasizes a humanistic, educative, and restorative character, and is technically reinforced by the Attorney General

Guideline No. 18 of 2021 on pre-prosecution procedures. However, since the guideline is internal in nature and does not hold a high position within the legal hierarchy, its substance needs to be elevated to the level of law to gain nationwide binding authority, ensure legal certainty, and achieve consistency in application.

This model prioritizes medical and social rehabilitation as the primary alternative to imprisonment, with a clear legal mechanism involving integrated assessment. Rehabilitation is positioned not merely as a discretionary policy of law enforcement officials but as a legal right of suspects/defendants guaranteed by law. Accordingly, the law functions dually: maintaining public order and legal certainty, while simultaneously promoting human development so that substance abusers can reintegrate productively into society.

Conceptually, the model of resolving narcotics offenses through rehabilitation with a restorative justice approach represents an integration of the philosophical foundation of the New Criminal Code, the technical mechanisms of law enforcement, and the law's role as a tool for societal reform. This model ensures that law enforcement is not merely repressive but restorative, protecting human rights and providing tangible benefits for offenders, victims, and the broader community.

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